

VETERINARY SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF COITUS DURATION ON CONCEPTION, GESTATION LENGTH, AND LITTER SIZE IN DOBERMAN DOGS

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Abstract

In practice, it has been shown that many factors influence successful insemination in bitches, as well as the length of gestation and litter size. Modern techniques have significantly improved insemination success. Checking the level of progesterone in the blood of bitches has greatly facilitated the determination of the optimal timing for successful insemination.

Fifty matings were analyzed in a Doberman breeding facility. The monitoring period spanned from November 2011 to the end of 2021. During this period, 18 bitches of varying ages, with different litter counts, were mated. Thirty-nine males of varying ages were used throughout the experiment, all of which were proven to be fertile.

Out of the 50 analyzed matings, 6 were not conducted based on the previously established progesterone level as an indicator of fertile days. Interestingly, the success rate of insemination in these matings was 100%. In all other matings, testing was performed beforehand.

Keywords: progesterone, matings, insemination

Introduction

In practice, it has been shown that many factors influence successful insemination in bitches, as well as the length of gestation and litter size. Modern techniques have significantly improved insemination success. Checking the level of progesterone in the blood of bitches has greatly facilitated the determination of the optimal timing for successful insemination (Concannon, 2011).

This way, the onset of ovulation can be predicted, which in turn allows for the prediction of gestation length. The due date occurs 64-66 days after ovulation, or 56-58 days after the onset of cytological diestrus (Kustritz, 2003). The concentration of progesterone at the time of the LH surge (36 to 48 hours before ovulation) is 1.5 to 2.5 ng/ml, 5 to 8 ng/ml at the time of ovulation, and after the completion of ovulation, it ranges from 10 to 25 ng/ml (England, 2010). Timely mating of the male and female certainly results in successful fertilization, which guarantees a large and healthy litter. A detailed examination of hormones in the blood can accurately determine the hormonal status related to reproduction, allowing for the organization of the desired mating accordingly (Senger, 2005).

The most visible peculiarity in the sexual act of dogs is the characteristic "tying," the union of the male

and female after the penetration of the male genital organ into the vagina. This phenomenon, specific to the canine species, results from the swelling of the penis's bulb, which, together with the contraction of the vaginal sphincter muscles, forms an inseparable bond that can last for varying periods, ranging from 3 to 30 minutes. After the initial "knot" connection, the male will dismount the female with his front legs and place one hind leg over her back, forming a position where they face away from each other (Stancic, 2007). During this period, ejaculation of seminal fluid into the vagina occurs. This position causes compression of the blood vessels in the penis, extending the time for the expulsion of seminal fluid, including all its fractions.

Materials and Methods

Fifty matings were analyzed in a Doberman breeding facility. The monitoring period spanned from November 2011 to the end of 2021. During this period, 18 bitches of varying ages, with different litter counts, were mated. Thirty-nine males of varying ages were used throughout the experiment, all of which were proven to be fertile. For the sake of accuracy and timely determination of fertile days based on progesterone levels in serum, monitoring was conducted daily. When the first signs of "standing reflex" appeared in the

females, progesterone analysis was performed. Based on the initial results, further actions were determined.

In the case of a low level, up to 2 ng/ml, the next test is performed after 2-3 days regardless of the "standing" reflex. If the progesterone concentration is between 2 ng/ml and 5 ng/ml, a repeat test is performed the following day. Before the copulation act itself, the females were allowed to satisfy their physiological needs. After the tying of the male and female, the duration was recorded. If necessary, non-invasive assistance was provided to prevent any damage to the reproductive tract of both individuals. In the tying position, the male and female remained connected until they separated on their own. At that moment, the separation time was recorded and considered as the duration of coitus. The female was kept calm and any exertion was prevented. In some cases, the hind legs and the back part of the body were raised to prevent the leakage of ejaculate. This position was maintained for about 5 minutes. After that, the female was closed off and not allowed to walk for the next 3-4 hours. After mating, the female remains in regular care, like other dogs in the breeding facility, until 25-30 days when an ultrasound examination is performed to confirm pregnancy (Johnston et al., 2001). In case of a positive result, the female is transitioned to a pregnancy regimen, which includes a diet tailored for this category, as well as separate but unrestricted movement until whelping.

The durations of coitus varied, ranging from 4 to 40 minutes. For easier analysis, they were divided into 4 groups. The first group consisted of matings with a

tying duration of up to 10 minutes, the second group included matings with a tying duration of 11 to 15 minutes. The third group contained results of matings with a tying duration of 16 to 20 minutes, and the fourth group consisted of matings where the tying time was over 21 minutes.

Results and Discussion

Out of the 18 observed females, one failed to conceive even after the third mating with three different males, while all the others had offspring. Out of the 50 analyzed matings, 6 were not conducted based on the previously established progesterone level as an indicator of fertile days. Interestingly, the success rate of insemination in these matings was 100%. In all other matings, testing was performed beforehand. Generally, successful insemination was observed in 36 matings, or 75%, which later resulted in whelping. In the remaining 12 matings, or 25%, there was no successful conception. The average progesterone level in all tested females was 9.39 ng/ml, while in those that were fertilized, the progesterone level was 9.01 ng/ml.

The progesterone level in the group of females that did not conceive was 10.34 ng/ml. Depending on the progesterone level in the blood, females were mated at different intervals, ranging from the same day when the progesterone level was determined to 3 days after progesterone testing. The average time to determine the progesterone level in the blood before copulation was 0.88 days.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Values

Group	Progesterone			Duration of Coitus			Duration of Gestation			Number of Puppies		
	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
Mean	9.45	9.59	10.88	8.16	13.00	21.48	63.00	62.55	62.72	8.01	7.05	8.66
Min	2.80	2.35	3.18	4.00	11.00	16.00	60.00	60.00	59.00	2.00	1.00	1.00
Max	23.36	17.90	46.00	10.00	15.00	40.00	66.00	65.00	67.00	14.00	12.00	16.00
SE	1.79	0.79	2.29	0.42	0.27	1.45	0.61	0.36	0.46	1.34	0.76	0.98
SD	6.46	3.72	9.73	1.51	1.38	6.67	1.94	1.60	2.02	4.03	3.32	4.30

Table 2. Summary of Examined Parameters

Parameter	Group			Total
	1	2	3	
Number of Matings	12	24	20	56
Average Progesterone Level	9.45	9.59	10.88	9.97
Average Duration of Coitus	8.16	13.00	21.48	15.00
Mating Success	75.00	75.00	90.00	80.00
Average Duration of Gestation	63.00	62.55	62.72	62.75
Average Number of Puppies	8.01	7.05	8.66	7.94

Table 3. Mating Success Results

Parameter	Total	Successful mating	Unsuccessful mating
Number of Litters	56	45	11
Percentage	100	80.35	19.65
Progesterone Level	9.97	9.90	10.32
Duration of Coitus	15.00	15.64	12.36
Duration of Gestation	62.75	62.75	/
Number of Puppies	7.94	7.94	/

The average duration of coitus, in 48 matings, was 14.35 minutes. The average tying time of the male and female, in successful matings, was 14.91 minutes, while in matings that did not result in pregnancy, the average was 12.66 minutes. The time of tying between the male and female up to 10 minutes was recorded in 10 females with an average duration of 8.1 minutes and a 80% insemination success rate. In this group, the average litter size was 8.37 puppies. The second and largest group consisted of 24 females with an average coitus duration of 12.87 minutes and an insemination success rate of 76.67%. The average litter size in this group was 7.5 puppies. The third group of females, represented by 9 individuals, had an average tying time of 17 minutes and an insemination success rate of 77.77%. This group had the highest average number of puppies born, at 9.71. The fourth group, consisting of 5 females, had an average coitus duration of 29.2 minutes and a 100% successful insemination rate. This group had the smallest average litter size of 6.75 puppies.

Conclusion

The overall average gestation length in the population of observed bitches is 62.63 days. The normal gestation length for bitches is between 58 and 63 days (Case, 2011). In the first group of females, the average gestation length is the longest at 63.12 days. In the second group, the average gestation length is 62.47 days,

and in the third group, it is 62.71 days. In the last group of bitches, with a tying duration of over 20 minutes, the average gestation length is the shortest at 62.25 days.

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